

POLYLACTIC ACID (PLA) AND SODIUM ALGINATE FILM PRODUCTION AND USAGE IN ACTIVE PACKAGING FOR TOMATO PRESERVATION

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Abstract: *Increasing food needs and decreasing food sources have made it necessary to protect food from pathogens and keep it fresh for a longer period. Active packages are used to increase the shelf life of food. Interest in biopolymeric film and edible antibacterial agents is increasing day by day due to migration in the active packaging system. Biopolymers are organic molecules that do not have a problem in contact with food. Polylactic acid, polyglycolic acid, polyvinyl alcohol, carrageenan, and starch are the most widely used biopolymers. Nanoparticles and metal contents as antimicrobial additives are being replaced by natural origin antimicrobial agents today. These include aromatic oils such as peppermint oil, cinnamon oil, and products of natural origin such as sodium alginate, nisin, chitosan. The aim of this study is to produce active packaging film to extend the shelf life of tomatoes by using sodium alginate and polylactic acid. In this study, films were produced by solvent casting method by adding 0, 1, 2.5, and 5% sodium alginate into 10% polylactic acid solution. The chemical structure of the produced films was determined by ATR-FTIR, transparency by visually, color properties by spectrophotometer, contact angle and surface energy by goniometer. In addition, the elongation tests of the produced films were carried out. Decomposition characteristics of tomatoes packed with the obtained films were determined at room temperature. As a result, it has been determined that the produced films have mechanical and surface properties that can be used in food packaging and extend the shelf life of tomatoes. It was concluded that as the amount of sodium alginate increases, the shelf life of tomatoes increases.*

Keywords: active packaging, sodium alginate, polylactic acid, food shelf life

1 INTRODUCTION

The effort to provide taste, texture, aroma, stability and perhaps most importantly, compliance with the palate in the foods that human beings have to consume in order to survive is a process that goes back to ancient times and continues increasingly today. The diversification of products with new production techniques, the increase in consumer demands and consumption rate, the increase of shelf life in perishable and risky foods, the necessity of production in seasonal products within a certain time interval have made it necessary to use different preservation methods and food additives. However, the determination of the negative effects of food additives on human health has led researchers to studies to increase the shelf life of foods without using additives (Shim et al., 2011). At this point, the most appropriate approach is to protect the shelf life of the food by means of the food packaging surrounding it and to keep the quality and freshness at the desired standards throughout the shelf life. The basic functions of a food packaging; to preserve the integrity of the food at every stage of the chain from production to consumption, to protect the food against the parameters that threaten quality and safety, to inform the consumer on issues such as product content and storage conditions. While the packaging that fulfills these functions was accepted in the past, it is insufficient to meet the changing consumer demands today. This situation leads manufacturers to new generation technologies such as modified atmosphere packaging, active and smart packaging (Kruijf et al., 2002).

Active packaging; it is the interaction of the packaging with both the foodstuff and its environment in order to extend the shelf life or ensure safety while maintaining the quality of the foodstuff. While active packaging systems are basically designed to provide microbial safety, they find a wide variety of uses due to their oxygen scavenger, ethylene remover and carbon dioxide absorber properties. Biodegradable polymers or plastics are used as packaging material in antimicrobial packaging. Considering environmental concerns, biodegradable composites such as chitosan, starch, gluten, or poly (lactic acid) come to the fore. The main function of a food packaging is to ensure the quality and safety of food during storage and transportation and to prevent factors and conditions such as pathogenic microorganisms, air, light, oxygen, and humidity from spoiling the food (Rhim et al., 2013). Food packaging should not absorb moisture into the product and should prevent moisture loss from the product. It should protect the food from microbial contamination and act as a barrier against the passage of other volatile compounds such as water vapor, oxygen, carbon dioxide and

flavors into the food (Han, 2005; Mauriello et al., 2005; Tornuk et al., 2015). Microbial spoilage, which shortens the shelf life of foods and makes them unusable, mostly occurs on the surface of the food and poses a significant threat to human health (Ayana & Turhan, 2010). In order to prevent these deteriorations, antimicrobial agents are used in the form of spraying, dipping or coating the food surface. However, these substances can quickly transition into food or become neutralized in food. For this reason, its usefulness in food is limited (Coma et al., 2002; Uttara et al., 2000). As consumers become much more conscious, the interest in food packaging systems has increased, where all these negativities are not experienced, and better quality and safe food preservation is possible. All these problems have made it inevitable to increase the tendency towards new generation food packaging materials and technologies such as bioplastic material technologies, edible film and coating materials, modified atmosphere packaging systems, active and smart packaging systems. Food safety is always among the priority areas and antimicrobial packaging systems play a very important role in ensuring quality and safety in food. The basic principle of antimicrobial packaging with traditional preservation methods is to prevent microbial growth. There are 3 ways to add antimicrobial additives to the packaging system or to gain antimicrobial function by using antimicrobial polymer material; release, absorption, and immobilization (Han, 2003). In the release, microorganism growth is inhibited by the migration of the antimicrobial agent into the food or into the headspace of the package. In absorption, essential factors for microbial growth are removed from the food system. In immobilization, there is no antimicrobial agent release, but growth is suppressed by contact with the surface. Immobilization is more effective in liquid foods than solids.

Poly(lactic acid)s are rigid thermoplastic and aliphatic polymers with semi-crystalline or amorphous structure. This polymer has a unique feature in that it has both polyethylene terephthalate (PET) characteristics and exhibits polypropylene (PP) feature (Henton et al., 2005). Another feature of polylactic acid is that it is a biodegradable polymer produced from starch-rich plant sources such as corn, sugar cane and wheat. In addition to these features, PLA has features such as environmental friendliness and biocompatibility; It provides potential use in plastic applications, packaging, agricultural products, disposable products, and medical field (Gupta et al., 2007).

Sodium alginates are components that have been used in the food industry for many years as a thickener, gelling agent, and colloidal stabilizer, as well as for the distribution and/or retention of various proteins and cells. Sodium alginates are a polyuronic saccharide produced as an extracellular matrix by certain soil bacteria (*Azotobacter vinelandii* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) isolated from the

cell walls of brown seaweed species (Phaeophyceae). Sodium alginate is a low-cost, biocompatible, and biodegradable polymer that can be separated into functional components such as β -D-mannuronic acid (M) and α -L-gluonic acid (G). It is coded as a food additive with the code E400. The solubility of sodium alginates in water depends on the pH of the solvent, the ionic strength of the medium, and the presence of gelling ions in the solvent. While alginic acid and calcium alginate are insoluble in water, ammonium alginate, potassium alginate and sodium alginate are soluble in water. For them to become soluble, protonated carboxylic acid groups and pH must be kept above certain critical values. It is used as an antibacterial in flour and pastry products (Kandirmaz, 2020). In this study, it was aimed to produce active packaging film and to determine its properties to extend the shelf life of tomatoes.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA), all other solvents, HCl and NaOH and sodium alginate were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2 Methods

For the preparation of active film, firstly 10% poly(lactic acid) solution was prepared in chloroform. Sodium alginate was added to the prepared solution in the ratios in Table 1 and mixed rapidly, and film formulations were prepared.

Table 1. Active film formulations.

Formulation	%10 PLA solution (%)	Sodium Alginate (%)
<i>F0</i>	100	0
<i>F1</i>	99	1
<i>F2</i>	97.5	2.5
<i>F3</i>	95	5

The resulting equal volumes of film mixtures were poured into the Teflon mold and set in 10 minutes at room temperature. A standard mold made of PTFE with a thickness of 5 mm and dimensions of 1500 mm x 1500 mm was used in film casting processes.

2.3 Characterization

Chemical characterization of the films obtained was done with Perkin Elmer Spectrum100 ATR-FTIR spectrophotometer. The surface properties of the films were determined with a Leica optical microscope. Thickness of the films was

measured using a digital micrometer (Mitotuyo 7327, Tokyo, Japan). The mean value was taken from ten replications across each film sample. Tensile tests of the produced films were determined standard tensile stress-strain tests to measure modules, ultimate tensile strength, and elongation at break. Standard tensile stress-strain experiments were performed at room temperature on a Materials Testing Machine Z010/TN2S, using a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min.

The wettability of active films was determined using the contact angle with the sessile water droplet method. The characteristics of surfaces were determined with contact angle (TAPPI T 458). Distilled water was used as standard wetting fluid in a Pocket Goniometer Model PG-X, (FIBRO Systems AB, Sweden), which was measured as a function of time. The program is of version 3.4. Images of water droplets were then recorded by using a CCD video camera. Surface energies were calculated on the contact angle by ASTM D5946 standard test method.

The color measurements of obtained films were made by CIEL*a*b* method using X-Rite eXact spectrophotometer according to ISO 12647-2: 2013 standard. The measurement conditions of the spectrophotometer are determined as polarization filter with 0°/ 45° geometry with 2 observer angle with D50 light source in the range of 400-700 nm. The difference between the colors of the different films were calculated according to formula 1 according to the CIE ΔE 2000 ISO 13655 standard.

$$\Delta E_{00} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta L'}{k_L S_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta C'}{k_C S_C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta H'}{k_H S_H}\right)^2 + R_T \frac{\Delta C'}{k_C S_C} \frac{\Delta H'}{k_H S_H}} \quad (1)$$

The obtained films were wrapped on tomatoes and the related tomatoes were kept at room temperature. The deterioration of tomatoes was evaluated visually and colorimetrically.

3 RESULTS

Films containing sodium alginate have been produced successfully. Chemical illumination of the produced films was done with ATR-FTIR. ATR-FTIR spectra of the films are given in Figure 1. When the ATR-FTIR spectra of Polylactic acid without sodium alginate (F0) is examined, carbonyl stretches at 1750 cm and C-O-C stretch bands at 1200 cm are clearly seen (Mele et al., 2019). It is clearly visible that the characteristic bands of Polylactic Acid are shown in all spectra of F1, F2, F3 films. Main peaks of sodium alginate, only the signal of C = O stretching at 1630 cm observed in composite films. These results suggest the successful

combination of sodium alginate in polylactic acid films. The results are consistent with the literature (Mortalo et al., 2023).

Figure 1. ATR-FTIR spectrums of active films.

SEM images of the obtained films were photographed and examined. It was determined that the surfaces of the films in all compositions had smooth and homogeneous distribution. Figure 2 shows the SEM image of the film containing the highest sodium alginate.

Figure 2. SEM images of F3 film.

The contact angles of the obtained films were measured, and the surface energies were calculated accordingly and given in Figure 3. When the figure is examined, the contact angle of F0 (the film containing only polylactic acid) is 73.8.

With the addition of sodium alginate into the film, the contact angle decreased and reached a maximum of 71.7. The reason for this is due to the hydrophilic groups of sodium alginate. As the number of hydroxyl groups in the environment increases (i.e., as the amount of sodium alginate increases), the contact angle decreases. The results are in line with the literature (Bhasney et al., 2017). As the contact angle of the films decreased, the surface energies increased. This is an expected result.

Figure 3. Contact angles of active films.

When Figure 4 is examined, the tensile properties of active films are shown. When the pure polylactic acid film is examined, it is seen that it has the highest tensile strength. With the addition of sodium alginate into the film, there was a noticeable decrease in tensile strength due to the increase in the crystalline structure. It is known that this is due to the polymorphism feature between PLA and sodium alginate (Zhang et al., 2008). For this purpose, it can be concluded that the polymeric film should contain minimum sodium alginate in order to be used in food packaging.

Figure 4. Tensile strength of active films.

The color and gloss properties of the obtained films were examined (Table 2) and it was determined that the films without sodium alginate were white and visually semi-permeable. With the addition of sodium alginate, the film colors shifted significantly towards yellow. As the amount of sodium alginate increased, as can be seen from the color difference, the yellow shift reached advanced levels. The gloss, on the other hand, increased slightly with the addition of sodium alginate, and then the gloss decreased depending on the surface roughness as the amount of sodium alginate added increased. In addition, the transparency remained visually semi-permeable.

Table 2. Active films color and gloss properties.

Sample	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE	Gloss
F0	87.09	0.57	-1.55		7.1
F1	72.24	1.86	10.65	14.55	7.9
F2	71.85	8.94	26.27	20.37	3.8
F3	78.99	6.90	28.76	21.15	1.9

Tomatoes were wrapped with F0, F3, and market film, and the freshness of the tomatoes was visually evaluated at 24°C for 15 days. In the evaluations, it was determined that the tomato in the market film visually shriveled, softened and deteriorated on the sixth day, the same deterioration rate was reached on the seventh day of the tomato wrapped in the F0 film, and the tomato wrapped in the F3 film reached the eleventh day. It was found that the resulting active film helped the tomato maintain its freshness for twice as long.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, active films were successfully produced using PLA and sodium alginate. The chemical structure of the produced films was clarified with ATR-

FTIR. The surface was examined by SEM, and it was determined that it had a homogeneous and smooth structure. The contact angle and surface energies of the obtained films were examined, and it was determined that the films were capable of printing with solvent-based flexo ink. The tensile strength of the films obtained was measured and it was determined that the tensile strength of the films decreased as sodium alginate was added. The addition of sodium alginate significantly shifted the color to yellow and reduced the gloss. All the active films obtained increased the shelf life of tomatoes, and it was determined that the film containing the most sodium alginate increased the shelf life of tomatoes approximately twice.

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